

DESIGN OF A TEXTILE LINEAR SPIRAL ANTENNA FOR MEDICAL IMAGING

S. A. MITILINEOS^{1,*}, S. G. VASSILIADIS¹, P. GRIMANIS¹, K. RIZOPOULOS¹, S. P. SAVVAIDIS¹, N. A. STATHOPOULOS¹, S. KURSUN², Ö. ATALAY², F. KALAOĞLU²

¹*Piraeus University of Applied Sciences (TEI of Piraeus), Department of Electronic Engineering, 250 Thivon & Petrou Ralli str., 12244 Aigaleo, GREECE*

²*Istanbul Technical University, Textile Technologies and Design Faculty, inonu caddesi No:67 34437 Beyoglu-Istanbul*

*smitil@teipir.gr

Abstract: *Following the rapid technology development on smart and electronic textiles, research on textile antennas has rapidly emerged during the last decade due to their numerous applications in the health and safety sectors. Integrated electronic components in textile structures enables the development of new products and services for commercial and tactical applications. Correspondingly, antenna systems that are either embedded in clothing or developed using textile materials are needed. However, the inherent impairments of antenna operability when integrated into garments (i.e. bending and crumbling due to the user's mobility) make the development of textile antennas a challenging task. Another important issue is the operation of antennas in close vicinity to the human body, which can be modeled as a large volume with electrical properties different than those of air. In this paper, we report a linear spiral antenna design with a sufficiently large bandwidth to support wireless communications in a multitude of available networks, and also the potential to be used for body scanning and medical imaging through microwave transmission and scattering measurements.*

Keywords: *Conductive Fabrics; Textile Antennas; Textile Electronics; Spiral Antennas; Medical Imaging.*

1. Introduction

Advances in conductive textile materials and wearable electronics have received great interest, mainly due to their applications in the fields of human safety, health monitoring and security. Smart textiles may be used as a platform carrying smart sensory and actuator systems, mainly for developing applications that interact with the user's body. A wearable sensory and communications system will comprise several components like sensors, actuators, processing units, energy supplies and a communication system. Most of these units are related to low-frequency activities, like body sensing, local data processing etc. [1-3].

Textile antennas have recently attracted significant research resources due to their potential to be used for communications and medical applications in a seamless manner [4-5]. However, RF and microwave medical imaging and communications requires the high frequency characterization of textile materials, which is a challenging task. The electromagnetic properties of antennas are sensitive to their geometry, dimensions and dielectric characteristics of the materials used [6-7]. Given that regular clothing use also involves bending, crumbling and other unforeseen anomalies on the shape of the antenna, it becomes evident that textile antennas developers need to overcome a demanding amount of limitations and restrictions. The respective research field is very active and ongoing research includes new materials and techniques for robustness, durability and credibility of designs.

Moreover, medical imaging has been proposed for health monitoring [8-9]. The electrical environment of an antenna system designed for biomedical sensing is essentially the human body, which is fundamentally different to that of a conventional antenna operating in free space. Antennas for medical applications are ultra-wideband antennas, in order to cover a large bandwidth for efficient impulse response measurements of transmission and scattering body characteristics. In this sense, the proposed ultra-wideband spiral antenna on top of being used for wireless communications in a multitude of networks, is also suitable for medical imaging and related applications.

In this paper, we examine the possibility of developing an antenna with ultra-wideband characteristics for incorporation into textiles. The concept is that with an extremely high frequency bandwidth, the antenna will remain functional even under bending and crumbling conditions. The proposed antenna design is that of a linear spiral antenna since it inherently exhibits wideband characteristics [10]. Due to their particular spiral design with extending arms of increasing width, spiral antennas provide efficient matching of incoming

signals over a large frequency range and also provide an efficient means of coupling with the environment and, hence, radiation. The fractional bandwidth of a spiral antenna may be as large as 30:1 and has a radiation pattern with a maximum at a direction perpendicular to the plane of the antenna. Due to the efficient coverage of a very large bandwidth, as well as their circular polarization, spiral antennas may be used in sensing applications despite their relatively lower achieved radiation gain. In the following Sections, we present the design of a proposed linear spiral antenna and its performance characteristics, as well as the technological background for its development using textile materials.

2. Design of a Linear Spiral Antenna and Numerical Results

The proposed linear spiral antenna has been designed following literature guidelines and optimized for operation from a frequency as low as 1 GHz up to more than 12 GHz. The antenna consists of a 1 mm thick wire with a linear radius increment factor equal to 0.6π cm per full rotation; the initial spiral radius is equal to 2.05 cm and each spiral branch extends for a total rotation of 13 rad. A layout of the antenna is presented in Figure 1(a).

Figure 1. (a) Layout of the proposed linear spiral antenna **(b)** Reflection coefficient of the proposed antenna in free space and 300 Ohm line impedance

The reflection coefficients of the antenna system (S_{11}) is displayed in Figure 1(b) for a feeding transmission line of characteristic impedance equal to 330 Ohm. It is noted that a conventional transmission line has a characteristic impedance of 50 Ohm; therefore, the proposed antenna needs an appropriate impedance transformation circuit and balun connected to its input in order to be efficiently fed. Furthermore, the upper frequency limit in Figure 2 is kept at 5 GHz due to processing power and memory limitations and compatibility with further numerical results presented in this paper.

The radiation pattern of the proposed antenna and the corresponding gain are illustrated in Figure 2(a-d) at 2, 3, 4, and 5 GHz respectively. The antenna exhibits satisfactory radiation characteristics and a strong gain that is larger than 5 dBi at 4 and 5 GHz.

Figure 2. Gain and radiation patterns of the proposed linear spiral antenna in free space and at (a) 2 GHz (b) 3 GHz (c) 4 GHz and (d) 5 GHz

Furthermore, the input reflection coefficient of the antenna was optimized for the case where its operating environment is not free space but a human body model instead. Two different body models were considered. The first is a simple box with dimensions dimensions 20 x 20 x 40 cm³ and electrical characteristics that correspond to breast fat (dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 4.10$, conductivity $\sigma=0.125$ S/m) [11-12]; the second is a more complex elliptical cylinders human body model that consists of a total of five layered elliptical cylinders of 40 cm height each; every cylinder corresponds to a different human body area. The outer cylinder, with area equal to 33.5 x 16.8 cm², corresponds to human skin with a dielectric constant 38.57 and a conductivity of 1.265 S/m [11-13]. Attached to the skin there is an inner cylinder that corresponds to fat, with an area of 32.5 x 15.2 cm², a dielectric constant of 5.33 and a conductivity of 0.086 S/m. Attached to the fat there is an inner more cylinder that corresponds to muscle, with an area of 31.0 x 14.2 cm², a dielectric constant of 53.29 and a conductivity of 1.4538 S/m. Then, there is a cylinder that corresponds to bone, with an area of 28.4 x 10.5 cm², a dielectric constant of 11.65 and a conductivity of 0.310 S/m. The innermost cylinder corresponds to internal organs and has an area of 27.2 x 8.4 cm², a dielectric constant of 53.38 and a conductivity of 1.912 S/m. Figure 3 illustrates the elliptical cylinders human body model as well as the setup for the simulation of the proposed antenna reflection coefficient in both model cases.

Figure 3. (a) Layout of elliptical cylinders human body model and (b) Setup for the simulation of the proposed antenna input reflection coefficient in the case of the elliptical cylinders human body model (c) Setup for the simulation of the proposed antenna input reflection coefficient in the case of the simple box human body model

Figure 4. Reflection coefficient of spiral antenna without human body model, with simple human body model and with elliptical cylinders human body model (for a feeding transmission line of 50 Ohm characteristic impedance)

The input reflection coefficient of the proposed linear spiral antenna for a feeding transmission line with a characteristic impedance of 50 Ohm is illustrated in Figure 4. It is interesting to note that while the input reflection coefficient of the proposed antenna is not matched for free space operation it is improved in the case of operation attached to a human body. The input reflection coefficient exhibits matching for both human body models for the entire frequency interval of 1-5 GHz while the reflection losses are even lower (lower than 15 dB) in the case of the more accurate elliptical cylinders human body model

3. Feasibility of Proposed Antenna Implementation with Textile Technology

Traditional textile manufacturing methods such as knitting, weaving, embroidery and printing are commonly employed to construct e-textile structures. However, the constituent materials and the type of textile structure should be specifically selected and tailored for their target application areas. Since textile-based antennas works as a bridge between components of e-textile structures and communication systems, special attention must be paid for their construction and performance properties in order to develop truly wearable systems.

In general, manufacturing of textile-based antennas should be classified as following:

- attaching of conductive tapes, e.g., copper tape, silver tape on non-conductive textile surfaces;
- attaching of metallized fabrics on non-conductive textile surfaces;

- applying of conductive materials on non-conductive textile structure using printing technology;
- the use of conductive yarns ,e.g., metal yarns, metal coated polymeric yarns to form knitted or woven textile antennas;
- construction of conductive pattern of textile-based antenna using embroidery technique.

While aforementioned methods may be applied to construct various type of textile based antennas, especially for the creation of patch type antennas, embroidery technology is more suitable to develop linear antennas due to the embroidered antennas prefer to flow along conductive yarns rather than from yarn to yarn [14]. Computer aided embroidery machine allows to manufacture repeatable designs with the accuracy of 1mm. Thus, proposed antenna design can be manufactured using this technology. Although the embroidery technique provides great freedom in the creation of conductive lines, conductive yarns should have relatively higher strength and flexibility due to the higher level of stress during the embroidery process [15]. It was found that while stainless steel yarn is not suitable for this technology, metal coated polymeric yarns enables creation of desired patterns [16].

On the other hand, printing technology may also be employed for the creation of proposed antenna design. However, it is a really challenging issue to create continuous conductivity due to the porosity and roughness of the textile structures. Also, during the bending and crumpling conditions, formation of cracks may cause discontinuity which adversely affects the antenna performance.

Overall, computer aided technology will be utilized to construct antenna structures. Silver plated nylon yarns with different linear resistances will be employed as conducting materials.

4. Conclusions

A linear spiral antenna design for medical imaging and wireless communications has been presented. The proposed antenna exhibits an ultra-wideband response and satisfactory reflection losses and gain. The implementation of the proposed antenna using textile materials will enable the integration in smart textile systems for biomedical applications in a light-weight and seamless manner.

5. Acknowledgement

The work in this paper was partially supported by the EU Marie Skłodowska-Curie RISE Project "Welding of E-Textiles for Interactive Clothing" (644268 -EtexWeld-H2020-MSCA-RISE-2014).

References

- [1] Symeonidis, S., Vassiliadis, S., Mitilineos, S. A., Potirakis, S., and Vossou, C., "On the feasibility and applications of wearable antennas", *International Istanbul Textiles Congress: Innovative and Functional Textiles*, pp. 1-5, May 30 – June 1, 2013, Istanbul, Turkey.
- [2] Stathopoulos, N.A., Savaidis, S.P., and Mitilineos, S.A., "RF measurements and characterization of conductive materials", appears in *Electronics and Computing in Textiles*, by Savvas K. Vassiliadis, editor; Ventus Publishing ApS, 2012.
- [3] Vassiliadis, S., Marmarali, A., Mitilineos, S.A., and Blaga, M., "Electromagnetic shielding with knitted fabrics", *Proceedings of the 46th International Congress of the International Federation of Knitting Technologists*, pp. 1-7, September 6-8, 2012, Sinaia, Romania.
- [4] P.J. Soh, G.A.E. Vandenbosch, X. Chen, P.S. Kildal, S.L. Ooi, H. Alikbarian, "Wearable textile antennas' efficiency characterization using reverberation chamber", IEEE, AP-S/URSI 2011.
- [5] Y. Ouyang, W. Chappell, "Measurement of electrotexiles for high frequency applications," Proc. IEEE MTT-S Int. Microwave Symposium, pp.1679-1682, 2005.
- [6] D. Cottet, J. Grzyb, T. Kirstein and G. Troster, "Electrical characterization of textile transmission lines", *IEEE Transactions on Advanced Packaging*, Vol. 26, No 2, 182-189, (2003).
- [7] Y. Ouyang, W. Chappell, "Measurement of electrotexiles for high frequency applications," Proc. IEEE MTT-S Int. Microwave Symposium, pp.1679-1682, 2005.
- [8] B. Stec, A. Dobrowolski, W. Susek, "Multifrequency microwave thermograph for biomedical applications", *Journal of telecommunications and Information Technology*, Volume 1, 2004, Pages 117–122.

- [9] X. Yun, E. Fear, and R. Johnston, "Compact antenna for radar-based breast cancer detection," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 53, no. 8, pp.2374-2380, 2005.
- [10] Piksa, P., and Mazanek, M., "A self-complementary 1.2 to 40 GHz spiral antenna with impedance matching", *Radioengineering*, Vol. 15, No. 3, pp. 1-5, September 2006.
- [11] D.Andreuccetti, R.Fossi, C.Petrucci, "An internet resource for the calculation of the dielectric properties of body tissues in the frequency range 10 Hz - 100 GHz", Italian National Research Council Institute for Applied Physics, Website at <http://niremf.ifac.cnr.it/tissprop/>. IFAC-CNR, Florence (Italy), 1997. Based on data published by C.Gabriel et al. in 1996.
- [12] <http://www.itis.ethz.ch/virtual-population/tissue-properties/overview/>
- [13] M. Lazebnik, E.L. Madsen, G.R. Frank, S.C. Hagness, "Tissue-mimicking phantom materials for narrowband and ultrawideband microwave applications", *Phys Med Biol.* 21;50 (18):4245-58, September 2005.
- [14] Tsois, Aris, et al. "Embroidery and related manufacturing techniques for wearable antennas: challenges and opportunities." *Electronics* 3.2 (2014): 314-338.
- [15] Orth, Margaret. "Defining flexibility and sewability in conductive yarns." *MRS Proceedings*. Vol. 736. Cambridge University Press, 2002.
- [16] Ghosh, T. K., A. Dhawan, and J. F. Muth. "Formation of electrical circuits in textile structures." *Intelligent textiles and clothing* (2006): 239-282.